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Understanding the multidimensionality of a concern for falling in people with unilateral trans-tibial amputation: A cross-sectional study --Manuscript Draft--

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Abstract:	<p>People with lower limb loss have a high risk of falling and often experience psychological concerns related to falling. A concern for falling is a multidimensional term that includes four subdomains: a fear of falling, self-efficacy, consequences of falling and perceptions of falls. There is limited knowledge in the literature about the delineation and association between subdomains in the concern for falling framework, and it is unknown if clinical factors and history of falls is associated with the concern for falling subdomains. This cross-sectional online survey evaluated the: 1) associations among different outcome measures for a concern for falling; 2) relationships between falls history with the different measures; and 3) clinical and demographic factors related with each outcome measure. Inclusion criteria: ≥ 18 years old, unilateral trans-tibial amputation and currently using a prosthesis for ambulation. Exclusion criteria: unable to provide informed consent. Eight standardized scales assessed a concern for falling: visual analog scale fear of falling, Modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in the Elderly, Activities-specific Balance Confidence scale, Falls Efficacy Scale International, Prosthetic Limb Users Survey – Mobility, Locomotor Capabilities Index, Consequences of Falling Scale and Perceived Ability to Manage Falls. The association among the eight concern for falling scales was performed using Pearson bivariate correlation analysis. The association of falls status on the scores was performed with t-tests. Multiple linear regression modelled the clinical and demographic factors related to each outcome measure. Sixty-eight adults (mean 61.8 ± 12.0) with unilateral trans-tibial amputation participated. Moderate statistically significant correlations were found across most outcome measures, with the strongest correlations found between the PLUS-M and mSAFFE ($r = -0.841$, $p < 0.001$), ABC and FES-I ($r = -10.821$, $p < 0.001$) and</p>

	PLUS-M and ABC ($r=0.819$, $p<0.001$). Faller status was not associated with any outcome measure ($p>0.05$). The R^2 for models examining the association of quality of life with fear of falling, avoidance of activities, self-efficacy and certainty to managing falls ranged between 0.27 and 0.47. Concern for falling should be evaluated independently of history of falls among PWLLL.
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1 **Understanding the multidimensionality of a concern for falling in people with unilateral**
2 **trans-tibial amputation: A cross-sectional study**

3 Running head: Concern for falling in transtibial amputees

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25 ABSTRACT

26 People with lower limb loss have a high risk of falling and often experience psychological
27 concerns related to falling. A concern for falling is a multidimensional term that includes four
28 subdomains: a fear of falling, self-efficacy, consequences of falling and perceptions of falls.
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30 subdomains in the concern for falling framework, and it is unknown if clinical factors and history
31 of falls is associated with the concern for falling subdomains. This cross-sectional online survey
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34 factors related with each outcome measure. Inclusion criteria: ≥ 18 years old, unilateral trans-
35 tibial amputation and currently using a prosthesis for ambulation. Exclusion criteria: unable to
36 provide informed consent. Eight standardized scales assessed a concern for falling: visual analog
37 scale fear of falling, Modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in the Elderly, Activities-
38 specific Balance Confidence scale, Falls Efficacy Scale International, Prosthetic Limb Users
39 Survey – Mobility, Locomotor Capabilities Index, Consequences of Falling Scale and Perceived
40 Ability to Manage Falls. The association among the eight concern for falling scales was
41 performed using Pearson bivariate correlation analysis. The association of falls status on the
42 scores was performed with t-tests. Multiple linear regression modelled the clinical and
43 demographic factors related to each outcome measure. Sixty-eight adults (mean 61.8 ± 12.0) with
44 unilateral trans-tibial amputation participated. Moderate statistically significant correlations were
45 found across most outcome measures, with the strongest correlations found between the PLUS-
46 M and mSAFFE ($r = -0.841$, $p < 0.001$), ABC and FES-I ($r = -0.821$, $p < 0.001$) and PLUS-M and
47 ABC ($r = 0.819$, $p < 0.001$). Faller status was not associated with any outcome measure ($p > 0.05$).

48 The R² for models examining the association of quality of life with fear of falling, avoidance of
49 activities, self-efficacy and certainty to managing falls ranged between 0.27 and 0.47. Concern
50 for falling should be evaluated independently of history of falls among PWLLL.

51

52 **Key words:** amputation, concern for falling, falls, prosthesis

53 INTRODUCTION

54 People with lower limb loss (PWLLL) have a high risk of falling, even for those who
55 have successfully completed a prosthetic rehabilitation program.[1] Over 50% of PWLLL sustain
56 at least one fall a year[2,3] and most falls occur while the person is walking with their
57 prosthesis[4]. The majority of PWLLL in Canada have a trans-tibial level amputation due to a
58 dysvascular etiology.[5] Risk factors for falls among PWLLL include increasing age, balance or
59 gait impairments, a higher level of amputation (e.g., trans-tibial compared to Symes or below
60 ankle) and a dysvascular amputation etiology.[1] Additionally, recalled number of falls, balance
61 confidence and perceived mobility are also associated with future falls in PWLLL.[6,7]

62 Falls for PWLLL can result in long-term adverse sequelae that affect both physical and
63 psychological function.[8,9] While the physical consequences of falls may be readily apparent to
64 the outside observer[10] (e.g., fractures, laceration, dehiscence of the stump wound), the
65 psychological effects require a thorough subjective history along with standardized
66 questionnaires to define and quantify the issue.[11] Amputee rehabilitation clinicians have
67 reported anecdotal concerns about the mismatch between patients' perceived concerns about
68 falling and their reported history of falls. To address this concern and reduce falls among
69 PWLLL, quantifying both concern for falling and falls history, and demonstrating the mismatch
70 to the patient, may be the most comprehensive approach. Therefore, assessing a concern for
71 falling both in relation to and independently of falls history is necessary to better understand this
72 issue in PWLLL.

73 Moore and Ellis[12] described a concern for falling as a multidimensional, overarching
74 term that includes multiple complex psychological effects, which are related but have distinct
75 elements that differentiates them from one another. The concern for falling framework was

76 adapted and applied to PWLLL by Nugent et al.[13] delineating five distinct subdomains: 1) fear
77 of falling (lasting concern about falling that leads an individual to avoid activities that they are
78 physically capable of performing); 2) falls efficacy (confidence in one's ability to perform
79 activities of daily living without falling); 3) mobility efficacy (confidence in one's ability to
80 perform normal daily activities without difficulty); 4) consequences of falling (feared outcomes
81 as a result of falling); and 5) perception of falls (an individual's knowledge of and belief in their
82 ability to have control over falling). Associations indicate relationships between two constructs.
83 A perfect association would suggest that one construct be used interchangeably with the other, as
84 both would address the same aspects.[14] However, when associations are not perfect, it
85 provides evidence that the constructs while related, capture distinct aspects.[14] This implies that
86 although there may be overlap, each construct has specific difference that are reflected in one
87 outcome measure but not the other.[14] Despite clear definitions of each of the concern for
88 falling subdomains, the terms have been used interchangeably in the literature.[15] Our previous
89 publications used the preliminary results of this larger database, which demonstrated the
90 statistically significant association with a concern for falling has on overall quality of life for
91 PWLLL, but did not fully explain the variance in the relationship.[13] Previous research has
92 shown that within each subdomain of a concern for falling, different outcome measures evaluate
93 distinct constructs, making it necessary to use multiple outcome measures to fully evaluate each
94 subdomain.[13]

95 The lack of differentiation in this terminology limits clinicians to accurately define a
96 concern for falling among PWLLL and the identification and implementation of intervention
97 strategies.[16] The existing literature related to a concern for falling in PWLLL has focused on
98 balance confidence, fear of falling and falls knowledge. Hunter et al.[17] found balance

99 confidence to be low among PWLLL after completing prosthetic rehabilitation and did not
100 improve at three months after discharge. Falls-related self-efficacy, the belief that a person can
101 perform an activity without falling, has been found to remain unchanged in the first 6 to 12
102 months after prosthetic rehabilitation despite a significant improvement in functional
103 mobility.[8,16] Miller et al.[9] found 49.2% of PWLLL living in the community reported a fear
104 of falling. Fear of falling contributes to a decreased falls-related self-efficacy that contributes to
105 the overall psychological concerns related to falls and decreased community participation.[16]

106 The literature on a concern for falling among PWLLL lacks comprehensive evaluation,
107 defined as assessing at least one outcome measure within each subdomain of the concern for
108 falling framework, of how these subdomains may be influenced by a history of falls. To address
109 this gap, an evaluation of the relationships between different subdomains of a concern for falling
110 among PWLLL is indicated. The objectives of the study were to evaluate the associations among
111 different outcome measures related to a concern for falling, to assess the relationship between
112 falls history and a concern for falling, and to examine the influence of clinical and demographic
113 factors on each of the outcome measures for a concern for falling.

114 It was hypothesized that the eight concern for falling outcome measures will have
115 moderate to strong statistically significant correlations with one another. Second, it was
116 hypothesized that history of falls will not be statistically significantly associated with each
117 concern for falling outcome measure. Finally, it was hypothesized that clinical and demographic
118 factors would be associated with outcome measures related to a concern for falling.

119 **METHODS**

120 **Study participants**

121 This cross-sectional study used a secure web-based survey platform (Qualtrics XM
122 (Provo, Utah)). Participants were recruited through the regional outpatient amputee rehabilitation
123 program at Parkwood Institute in London, Ontario, Canada. To be eligible for this study,
124 participants were: 18 years of age or older, had a unilateral trans-tibial amputation, currently
125 using a prosthesis for ambulation, able to provide informed consent and had functional use of
126 English. Exclusion criteria were not currently using a prosthesis for mobility and being medically
127 unstable as determined by the treating physician. Recruitment for the study occurred between
128 October 2020 and May 2023. The study was approved by the Health Sciences Research Ethics
129 Board at the University of Western Ontario. The landing page of the online survey was the letter
130 of information and consent outlined that by completing the questionnaire people were consenting
131 to participate in the study. The Checklist for Reporting Results of Internet E-Surveys
132 (CHERRIES) was used in the writing of this manuscript.[18]

133 **Design and Development**

134 The survey was developed and piloted by the investigators who have extensive clinical
135 and research experience in the area of amputee rehabilitation. The survey comprised six sections:
136 i) eligibility, ii) demographic and clinical characteristics, iii) fear of falling, iv) self-efficacy, v)
137 consequences of falling and vi) control over falling.

138 **Outcome Measures**

139 a) ***Demographic and Clinical Information***. The following information was collected: age,
140 gender, number of prescription medications (as proxy for comorbidity burden), amputation
141 information (i.e., etiology, Socket Comfort Score), history of falls in the past 12 months (a fall
142 was defined as unintentionally coming to rest on the ground, floor or other lower level[19]),

143 prosthesis use, quality of life (overall score from World Health Organization Quality of Life
144 scale – WHOQOL-BREF[20]) and gait aid use.

145 b) ***Fear of Falling***: Two outcome measures were used to evaluate fear of falling. The first asked
146 participants to rate their fear of falling using a visual analog scale from 0 to 100 with higher
147 values indicating a greater concern.[21] The Modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in
148 the Elderly (mSAFFE) evaluated avoidance of activities due to a perceived fear of falling.[22]
149 The scale has 17 questions evaluated with a 3-point Likert scale (1, would never avoid; 2,
150 sometimes avoid; and 3, always avoid). The final score is the sum of all the item scores with
151 higher scores indicating a worse fear of falling. The mSAFFE has demonstrated good reliability
152 in PWLLL.[22]

153 c) ***Self- Efficacy***: Four outcome measures were used to evaluate the domain of self-efficacy. The
154 first outcome measure was The Falls Efficacy Scale – International (FES-I), a 16-item self-report
155 measure of the participant’s level of a concern for falling when performing physical and social
156 activities.[23] Items are rated on a 4-point Likert scale (1, not at all concerned; 2, somewhat
157 concerned; 3, fairly concerned; and 4, very concerned). The overall score is the sum of the 16-
158 items for a possible score ranging from 16 to 64. A higher score indicates a worse falls efficacy.
159 The FES-I has demonstrated good reliability in PWLLL.[21]

160 The Activities-specific Balance Confidence (ABC) Scale is a 16-item self-report measure
161 that quantifies balance confidence in various activities of daily living.[24] Items are rated on a
162 scale from 0 to 100%, where a score of 0% indicates no confidence and a score of 100%
163 indicates complete confidence they will not become unsteady or lose their balance. The overall
164 score is the sum of all the questions divided by 16. A high score indicates better balance
165 confidence. The ABC Scale has good reliability and construct validity in PWLLL.[25]

166 Two measures of mobility efficacy were administered, the Prosthetic Limb Users Survey
167 of Mobility (PLUS-M) and the Locomotor Capabilities Index in Amputees (LCI). The PLUS-M
168 was developed specifically for PWLLL and contains 12 questions that evaluate the level of
169 difficulty a participant has performing an activity while wearing their prosthesis.[26] Scores are
170 converted to a percentile with higher scores indicating better function. Validity and normative
171 scores have been established for the PLUS-M.[26] The LCI is a subscale of the Prosthetic Profile
172 of the Amputee questionnaire and comprises 14 questions that evaluate ability to perform
173 functional activities while wearing their prosthesis scored on a 5-point Likert scale (0, unable to
174 do and 5, able to do alone without ambulation aids).[27] The total score is the sum of the items
175 with scores ranging from 0 to 56, higher scores indicating better prosthesis mobility. The
176 Prosthetic Profile of the Amputee questionnaire has demonstrated reliability and validity.[27]

177 **d) Consequences of Falling:** The Consequences of Falling (CoF) Scale is a 12-item tool that
178 evaluates perceived concerns about what might happen after a person sustains a fall.[22] Each
179 question is scored on a 4-point Likert scale (1, disagree strongly; 2, disagree; 3, agree; and 4,
180 agree strongly). There are two subscales within the CoF Scale, damage to identity and functional
181 limitations. Each subscale is the total of the items in that section with scores ranging from 6 to
182 24, higher scores indicating worse perceived consequences to falling. The total score is the sum
183 of the two subscales with scores ranging from 12 to 48. The CoF Scale has demonstrated good
184 reliability in PWLLL.[21]

185 **e) Control over falling:** The Perceived Ability to Manage Falls (PAMF) was used to evaluate a
186 person's certainty about managing falls in terms of avoiding falls and handling any falls they
187 experience.[28] The PAMF has 4 questions that are scored using a 4-point Likert scale (1,
188 disagree strongly; 2, disagree; 3, agree; and 4, agree strongly) with higher scores indicating a

189 better ability to manage if they should fall. The PAMF has demonstrated good reliability in
190 PWLLL.[21]

191 **Data Analysis**

192 Data from the Qualtrics software were exported into an Excel file (Microsoft Corp.,
193 Redmond, Washington) and then imported into IBM SPSS software (version 27, IBM Corp.
194 Armonk, New York) for statistical analysis. A priori it was established that any surveys with less
195 than 80% of survey items completed would be removed from the analysis. Categorical responses
196 were summarized using frequencies and percentages, and continuous variables were summarized
197 with means and standard deviations. The mean total scores and standard deviations of the eight
198 outcome measures were calculated. Scores were converted to a percentage of the maximum
199 score, except the PLUS-M which is already converted into a percentile as the final score, for
200 graphical presentation in a radar plot.

201 To address the first objective of evaluating the associations among different outcome
202 measures related to a concern for falling, the following two analyses were performed. First, the
203 tasks within the multi-item outcome measures of mSAFFE, ABC, FES-I, LCI and PLUS-M were
204 summarized in a table for identification of items evaluated across the scales. Second, Pearson
205 bivariate correlation analysis was performed on the total scores of the eight outcome measures
206 ($p < 0.001$ was set as statistical significance to address multiple comparisons) Pearson bivariate
207 correlation values of 1 are considered perfect; values of 0.80 through 0.99 are considered strong;
208 values 0.60 through 0.79 are considered moderate; values of 0.30 through 0.59 are considered
209 fair; and values of < 0.29 are considered poor.[29]

210 For the second objective of assessing the relationship between falls history and a concern
211 for falling, the sample was stratified by faller status (recurrent faller (≥ 2 falls) and non-

212 fallers/single fallers). The total scores on the eight outcome measures were compared between
213 the faller status groups using independent t-tests.

214 For the third objective of examining the influence of clinical and demographic factors on
215 each of the outcome measures for a concern for falling, backward stepwise linear regression was
216 used to model the factors that are associated with the total scores of each of the outcome measure
217 (probability to enter was set at $F \leq 0.05$ and probability to remove was set at $F \geq 0.100$) for a total
218 of eight models. Explanatory independent variables of interest were age, gender, recurrent falls
219 history (≥ 2) in past 12 months (yes/no), gait aid use (yes/no), number of prescription
220 medications, WHOQOL-BREF total quality of life score. Statistical significance was set at
221 $p < 0.05$.

222 **RESULTS**

223 A total of 68 people completed the survey, and their data were analyzed (Table 1). The
224 average age was 61.8 ± 12.0 years, 67.6% self-identified as a man and the majority had an
225 amputation etiology of diabetes (38.2%). Sixteen (23.5%) people reported their amputation
226 etiology as “Other” without describing in full the cause. A total of 39 (57.4%) people reported
227 sustaining at least one fall in the previous 12 months. The average number of falls was $4.4 (\pm 5.5)$
228 with 12 people sustaining a single fall and 25 having recurrent falls (2 or more). The average
229 reported quality of life score was 3.5 ± 0.9 out of 5.

230 The average score on the fear of falling visual analog scale was 36.2 ± 30.9 , scores ranged
231 from 0 to 100. The average score for the mSAFFE was 25.4 ± 7.0 , scores ranged from 17 to 42.
232 The average FES-I score was 28.3 ± 10.9 , scores ranged from 16 to 61. The average score for the
233 ABC scale was $73.4 \pm 22.3\%$, scores ranged from 0 to 100%. The average score for the CoF scale
234 was 24.5 ± 7.1 , scores ranged from 14 to 47. The sub-score for “loss of functional independence”

235 was 10.6 ± 4.4 and the “damage to identity” sub-score was 14.1 ± 4.0 . The total PAMF score was
236 15.7 ± 2.9 , scores ranged from 5 to 20. The average LCI score was 44.3 ± 13.5 with scores ranging
237 from 0 to 56. The average PLUS-M score was 45.4 with scores ranging from 31.2 to 71.4 (Figure
238 1).

239 The findings for objective one found that the tasks within the mSAFFE, ABC, FES-I,
240 LCI and PLUS-M are not completely duplicated across scales (see table, Supplement Digital
241 Content 1, which compares activities across five concern for falling scales). Tasks repeated
242 across three or more scales were: walking up and down stairs, cleaning the house, walk in a
243 crowded/busy space, and walk on a slippery surface. The bivariate correlation analysis
244 demonstrated statistically significant associations across all outcome measure total scores. The
245 strongest correlation value was between the ABC and FES-I (-0.821 , $P < 0.001$) (Table 2).

246 Analyses for the second objective found there was no statistically significant difference
247 between any of the outcome measures when the total scores were stratified by faller status
248 ($p > 0.05$) (Table 3). A sensitivity analysis of scores across three groups (i.e., non-fallers, single
249 fallers, recurrent fallers) also did not find a statistically significant association.

250 Objective three findings from the linear regression modelling for the factors significantly
251 associated to the eight outcome measures are listed in Table 4. Four variables had a statistically
252 significant association to many of the eight outcome measures: quality of life (all 8 models),
253 number of prescription medications (3 models), gait aid use (1 model) and recurrent falls history
254 (1 model). As quality-of-life scores decreased there was an increase in fear of falling and
255 avoidance of activities, reduced falls efficacy, and greater concern about the consequences of
256 falls. As quality-of-life scores increased there was an increase in balance confidence, mobility
257 efficacy, and a certainty about managing any falls. An increasing number of prescription

258 medications was associated with reduced mobility efficacy and reduced certainty about
259 managing any falls. The use of a mobility aid was associated with increased balance confidence.

260 **DISCUSSION**

261 This study evaluated a comprehensive set of outcome measures for a concern for falling
262 in a sample of people with unilateral trans-tibial limb loss. The outcome measures were
263 consistently aligned across the subdomains; low fear of falling was associated with high balance
264 confidence, lower activity avoidance, stronger falls efficacy, better mobility efficacy, increased
265 agency to prevent falls and fewer concerns regarding adverse consequences. While the total
266 scores for the eight outcome measures were moderately correlated, the items within each
267 measures were moderately correlated, the individual items within each measure were not
268 uniformly repeated across all the scales.

269 While the total scores for the eight outcome measures were moderately correlated, the
270 items within each measure were not uniformly repeated across all the scales. Recurrent faller
271 status in the last 12 months was not statistically significant to any of the outcome measure total
272 scores. However, quality of life was associated with total scores for all outcome measures in the
273 linear regression modelling. Specifically, increasing quality of life was associated with less fear
274 of falling, less avoidance of activities, better self-efficacy and better certainty in managing any
275 falls the person might experience.

276 Consistent with Moore and Ellis[12] review of psychological constructs in falls, we
277 found moderate correlations among the total eight outcome measures covering five subdomains
278 of a concern for falling. While the constructs are related within the concern for falling
279 framework, they are distinct from one another, and terminology for each construct is not
280 interchangeable[11] nor perfectly correlated[12]. It is crucial for researchers to ensure that the

281 instruments they use align with the specific constructs they aim to assess. To ensure consistency
282 across research and clinical practice, the construct being measured, and the instrument being
283 used to measure, are aligned with the construct of interest.[15] Clinicians evaluating a concern
284 for falling in PWLLL should incorporate multiple outcomes measures to comprehensively
285 evaluate the constructs of each subdomain. Using a variety of tools captures unique elements of a
286 concern for falling, which may be missed by a single scale, and provides a more holistic view of
287 the patient's needs.

288 Importantly, there was no association between faller status and scores on the concern for
289 falling outcome measures in our study, suggesting that falls history may not be the sole or most
290 accurate predictor of falls risk in PWLLL. Consistent with falls prevention and management
291 guidelines in older adults,[30] it is important to ask about a concern for falling in combination
292 with physical function assessment and history of falls.

293 Falls in PWLLL have well-documented physical and psychological consequences.[31]
294 The psychological impact of falls, including self-imposed activity restrictions, can lead to a
295 decrease in muscle strength, balance and gait problems, reduced endurance, social isolation and
296 decreased quality of life.[8] These psychological effects can both result from and contribute to
297 future falls. Barnett et al.[32] demonstrated that lower objective measures of postural stability
298 was associated with lower future falls efficacy measured at 6 months from baseline.
299 Additionally, recent research by Tobaigy et al.[6,7] has reported a relationships between physical
300 function, balance confidence, and mobility efficacy in predicting future falls in PWLLL.

301 Previous research has demonstrated that PWLLL who have completed a prosthetic
302 rehabilitation program exhibited a gap between their knowledge of falls and how to prevent
303 falls.[33] The relationship between the identification of barriers and facilitators to the

304 implementation of falls prevention strategies on a concern for falling warrants research to define
305 effective strategies for use in rehabilitation of PWLLL.

306 Higher quality of life was associated with positive shifts across all subdomains of a
307 concern for falling, highlighting the importance of viewing rehabilitation and community
308 integration that focuses on both physical and psychological needs of PWLLL. Previous research
309 has shown that despite PWLLL completing a comprehensive prosthetic rehabilitation program,
310 they often exhibit gaps in their knowledge of falls prevention strategies.[33] Addressing these
311 gaps through targeted interventions could enhance falls prevention and promote greater social
312 engagement, as high balance confidence has been shown to increase participation in social
313 activities.[13]

314 Several limitations should be noted. This was a convenience sample of people who
315 attended our facility's outpatient amputee rehabilitation program and does not represent all
316 people who attend our facility or all PWLLL. The study focused on people with a trans-tibial
317 amputation to limit heterogeneity, as bilateral and trans-femoral amputations are associated with
318 different capabilities for gait, balance, falls risk and prosthesis use.[34] Future studies should
319 adopt a multi-center approach to recruit participants with various levels of limb loss that allow
320 for subgroup analyses based on the level of amputation. Finally, a limitation of this study is the
321 lack of precision in the participant clinical factor responses, as it did not account for more
322 detailed reporting on prosthesis fitting and time since discharge from prosthetic rehabilitation,
323 which warrants further exploration. Despite these limitations, this study has several strengths.
324 The outcome measures used in this study represent measures that are used in clinical and
325 research practice in this population. Two measures were included among the complement of tests
326 that were developed specifically for PWLLL. Future research should evaluate the validity of

327 content among the remaining measures. The outcome measures used in this study have
328 psychometric properties acceptable for use in PWLLL and have reliability values for use in an
329 online format. This study contributes to the growing body of literature by providing an in-depth
330 assessment of the psychological and physical constructs associated with concern for falling in
331 PWLLL which will inform future interventions and clinical practice.

332 **CONCLUSION**

333 This study evaluated a comprehensive set of outcomes measures for a concern for falling
334 in people with unilateral trans-tibial limb loss. Many of the concern for falling outcome measures
335 demonstrated moderate and statistically significant associations to one another but were not
336 perfectly aligned in terms of their correlation or item content. Therefore, they should not be used
337 interchangeably to evaluate the same construct. There was an alignment of scores across the
338 scales, such that a low fear of falling was correlated with a high balance confidence, low activity
339 avoidance, good falls efficacy, good mobility efficacy, high agency to prevent falls and a low
340 concern of adverse consequences. Recurrent faller status in the last 12 months was not associated
341 to any of the outcome measure total scores. Higher quality of life was associated with less fear of
342 falling, less avoidance of activities, better self-efficacy and better certainty in managing any falls
343 the person might experience.

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465 **Table and Figure Legend:**

466 **Table 1.** Demographic and clinical characteristics of a sample of community-dwelling adults
467 with unilateral trans-tibial amputation. (n=68)

468 **Table 2.** Results of bivariate Pearson correlation analysis of eight outcome measures of a
469 concern for falling in unilateral trans-tibial amputees.

470 **Table 3.** Concern for falling outcome measure total scores reported for whole sample and
471 stratified by falls history in past 12 months among people with unilateral trans-tibial
472 amputations. (n=68)

473 **Table 4.** Results of step-wise linear regression modelling to identify factors associated with total
474 scores on measures of a concern for falling in unilateral trans-tibial amputees. (n=68)

475 **Figure 1.** Radar plot of total average scores as a percent of the maximum score on eight
476 measures of a concern for falling in people with a unilateral trans-tibial amputation. (n=68)

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Figure 1.

Table 1.

Characteristic	Mean (SD) or Frequency (n, %)
Age (years)	61.8 (12.0)
Gender	
- Man	46 (67.6%)
- Woman	22 (32.4%)
Number of prescription medications	6.0 (4.6)
Education	15.6 (3.7)
Recurrent falls (≥ 2) in last 12 months (yes)	39 (57.4%)
Amputation etiology	
- Peripheral vascular disease	5 (7.4%)
- Diabetes	26 (38.2%)
- Trauma	16 (23.5%)
- Failed surgery	3 (4.4%)
- Cancer	0
- Congenital defect	2 (2.9%)
- Other	16 (23.5%)
Length of time since amputation (years)	7.9 (11.9)
Socket Comfort Score	7.4 (2.0)
Prosthesis Wear	
- Day per week	7.0 (0.4)
- Hours per day	12.9 (3.6)
Use prosthesis for walking	68 (100%)

Walking aids (yes, %)	36 (52.9%)
Overall quality of life (score 0-100)	72.3

Table 2.

	VAS	mSAFFE	FES-I	ABC	PLUS-M	LCI	CoF	PAMF
VAS								
mSAFFE	0.791**							
FES-I	-0.757**	0.808**						
ABC	-0.698**	-0.783**	-0.821**					
PLUS-M	-0.717**	-0.841**	-0.729**	0.819**				
LCI	-0.329*	-0.517**	-0.376*	0.474**	0.579**			
CoF	0.669**	0.645**	0.701**	-0.624**	-0.668**	-0.410**		
PAMF	-0.531**	-0.434**	-0.523**	0.439**	0.453**	0.436**	-0.729**	

ABC, Activities-specific Balance Confidence Scale; CoF, Consequences of Falls Scale; FES-I, Falls Efficacy Scale International; mSAFFE, modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in the Elderly; PLUS-M, Prosthetic Limb User Survey – Mobility; LCI, Locomotor Capabilities Index; PCOF, Perceived Control over Falling Scale; PAMF, Perceived Ability to Manage Falls Scale; Fear of Falling VAS, visual analogue scale. 2-tailed bivariate analysis with *, correlation is significant at the level of <0.01 and correlation is significant at the level of ** <0.001.

Table 3.

Outcome Measure	Total Sample (n=68)	Falls History in the Previous 12 months		t test comparison on faller status
		Non-Fallers & Single Fallers (n=29)	Recurrent Falls (2+) (n=39)	p-value
Fear of Falling				
VAS	36.2 (30.9)	41.2 (33.1)	32.4 (29.0)	0.248
mSAFFE	25.4 (7.0)	26.9 (7.1)	24.3 (6.8)	0.131
Self-Efficacy				
ABC	73.4 (22.3)	77.2 (22.5)	68.3 (21.4)	0.104
FES-I	28.3 (10.9)	28.1 (11.5)	28.5 (10.2)	0.882
Mobility Efficacy				
PLUS-M	45.4 (11.0)	47.5 (9.7)	42.5 (12.1)	0.063

LCI	44.3 (13.5)	46.8 (12.1)	40.7 (14.8)	0.066
Consequences				
CoF	24.8 (7.0)	23.9 (6.1)	25.9 (8.1)	0.249
Control over Falling				
PAMF	15.6 (2.9)	15.7 (3.1)	15.5 (2.7)	0.782

Note: ABC, Activities-specific Balance Confidence Scale; CoF, Consequences of Falls Scale; FES-I, Falls Efficacy Scale International; mSAFFE, modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in the Elderly; LCI, Locomotor Capabilities Index; PCOF, Perceived Control over Falling Scale; PAMF, Perceived Ability to Manage Falls Scale; Fear of Falling VAS, visual analogue scale from 0 (no fear) to 100 (worst fear). High scores for mSAFFE, FES-I, CoF indicate worse outcomes. High scores on VAS, ABC, PLUS-M, LCI and PAMF indicate good outcomes.

Table 4.

Regression Model	Outcome Measure	Explanatory Variables	Unstandardized β Coefficient (95% CI)	p-value	R² for Model
Fear of Falling					
1	Visual analog scale	Falls history	21.5 (2.46, 40.46)	0.028	0.44
		Quality of Life	-0.80 (-1.15, -0.45)	<0.001	
2	mSAFFE	Quality of Life	-0.14 (-0.22, -0.06)	0.001	0.30
Self-Efficacy					
3	ABC	Quality of Life	0.37 (0.13, 0.61)	0.004	0.34
		Gait aid use	15.08 (1.09, 29.07)	0.036	
4	FES-I	Quality of Life	-0.29 (-0.40, -0.17)	<0.001	0.47
Mobility Efficacy					
5	PLUS-M	Quality of life	0.14 (0.01, 0.28)	0.041	0.44
		Number of medications	-0.68 (-1.42, 0.07)	0.073	
6	LCI	Quality of life	0.14 (-0.02, 0.29)	0.085	0.32
		Number of medications	-1.16 (-2.02, -0.29)	0.011	

Consequences					
7	CoF	Quality of life	-0.20 (-0.28, -0.12)	<0.001	0.47
Control over falling					
8	PAMF	Quality of life	0.08 (0.05, 0.11)	<0.001	0.27
		Number of medications	-0.17 (-0.34, 0.01)	0.057	

Note: ABC, Activities-specific Balance Confidence Scale; CoF, Consequences of Falls Scale; FES-I, Falls Efficacy Scale International; mSAFFE, modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in the Elderly; PLUS-M, Prosthetic Limb User Survey – Mobility; LCI, Locomotor Capabilities Index; PCOF, Perceived Control over Falling Scale; PAMF, Perceived Ability to Manage Falls Scale; Fear of Falling VAS, visual analogue scale from 0 (no fear) to 100 (worst fear). High scores for mSAFFE, FES-I, CoF indicate worse outcomes. High scores on VAS, ABC, PLUS-M, LCI and PAMF indicate good outcomes. Variables entered into the step-wise linear regression modelling were age, gender, falls history in past 12 months (yes/no), gait aid use (yes/no), number of medications, quality of life, amputation etiology, Socket Comfort Score.

Supplemental Digital Content 1. Comparison of activities evaluated across the multi-item scales use to assessment subdomains for a concern of falling.

	mSAFFE	ABC	FES-I	LCI	PLUS-M
	Fear avoidance	Balance confidence	Falls efficacy	Mobility efficacy	Mobility efficacy
Task					
Get dressed and undressed			x		
Taking a bath or shower			x		
Taking a bath	x				
Taking a shower	x				
Get in and out of chair	x		x	x	
Get up off the floor if fell				x	
Walk around house	x	x		x	x
Go to answer the phone before it stops ringing			x		
Walk up and down stairs (use of handrail not stated)	x	x	x		

Walk up and down stairs with use of handrail				x	
Walk up stairs without use of handrail				x	
Walk downstairs without use of handrail				x	
Bend over to pick up something from floor	x	x	x	x	
Reach for small can off shelf at eye level		x			
Prepare simple meals	x		x		
Reach for something over head or on ground	x		x		
Stand on tiptoes and reach over head		x			
Stand on chair and reach for something		x			
Sweep the floor/cleaning the house	x	x	x		
Walk outside the house to car in driveway		x			
Walk around the neighbourhood	x		x	x	
Walk half mile	x				
Go to the shops	x		x		
Get in and out of car		x			
Take public transport	x				

Walk across parking lot		x			
Walk up and down ramp/slope		x	x		
Step up curb				x	
Step down curb				x	
Step up and down curbs					x
Visit a friend or relative	x		x		
Go to doctor or dentist	x				
Walk carrying an object				x	x
Walk in crowded mall/busy place	x	x	x		
Able to keep up with others while walking					x
Go to social event	x		x		
Walk in dimly lit and unfamiliar place	x				x
In busy space where you are bumped into by people		x			x
Step on and off escalator holding onto railing		x			

Step on and off escalator without holding onto railing		x			
Walk outside on even surface				x	
Walk on uneven surface			x	x	x
Walking on a slippery surface (wet, ice, snow)	x	x	x		x
Walk outside in inclement weather				x	
Exercising	x				
Move a chair from one room to another					x
Walk on steep gravel path					x
Walk 2 miles on an even surface					x

Note: ABC, Activities-specific Balance Confidence Scale; FES-I, Falls Efficacy Scale International; mSAFFE, modified Survey of Activities and Fear of Falling in the Elderly; PLUS-M, Prosthetic Limb User Survey – Mobility; LCI, Locomotor Capabilities Index.